

Body Sensations as Design Material: An Approach to Design Sensory Technology for Altering Body Perception

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ABSTRACT

Sensory technologies alter how we perceive our body, which can have profound implications for multiple domains. Prior work has contributed a myriad of artefacts and evaluative studies, but we still lack design knowledge to design meaningful body perception alterations facilitated by sensory technologies. To address this gap, we draw from soma design to propose a methodological approach centered on body sensations as design material. We articulate our approach based on a project on co-designing wearables to alter body perception together with professional dancers. Our approach involves engaging participants in articulating and sharing body sensations to others, and exploring somatically sensory stimuli to co-design concepts for future technologies. We contribute experiential facets of body sensations, movement and sensory potentials to alter sensations, methods and design strategies, and a collection of ideas. Our work can be relevant to design communities interested in sensory technologies, perceptual alterations and body sensations as material.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Interaction design process and methods.**

KEYWORDS

Body Perception, Body Sensations, Design Material, Sensory Technology, Soma Design, Wearables

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1 INTRODUCTION

The technologies and interactions we design profoundly influence our body experiences [30]. Research both in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and cognitive neuroscience has shown that sensory technologies can significantly impact body perception — how we perceive our own body size, shape, capabilities. Our body perception is highly plastic and can be altered through multisensory signals and feedback related to the body [9, 20, 53, 82, 102, 114], through which it is possible to create e.g. perceptual illusions of one's physical body changing [69, 94, 118]. For example, altering the frequency of people's own footstep sounds makes them feel changes in their perceived body weight and impacts on their e.g. gait, emotions, and feelings of being lighter and quicker [16, 99].

This insight has spurred a wealth of research contributing various inspirational ultimate particulars and corresponding evaluative studies (e.g. [6, 16, 40, 48, 68, 76, 85, 87, 95, 103, 118]), opening up for numerous application areas - from potential health and well-being interventions (e.g., physical inactivity [47, 49]; body image disorders [61, 96], physical rehabilitation [85]) to interactive arts and creativity [21, 114, 115]. These efforts have been instrumental in probing and validating in the lab the potential of sensory technologies to alter body perception, as well as in uncovering the complex perceptual processes driving these changes. Yet, this extensive research area still lacks methodological *design knowledge* to help designers explore and design interactive sensory experiences that meaningfully alter body perception. As these technologies become

more accessible and ubiquitous in real-life contexts, it becomes increasingly important to ask *how can we identify and articulate relevant body perceptions that we want to alter through design? How can we explore the potential of different sensory stimuli to alter people's perception of their own body? How can we generate concepts for future interactive experiences that foster meaningful alterations?*

Here, we propose a methodological approach to start addressing these questions. Drawing from soma design [30], we propose to frame the design inquiry on **body sensations as design material** that can help people identify, articulate and explore in depth interesting interplays between sensory stimuli and body perception alterations. We propose our approach based on the work in a project aimed at designing multisensory wearables to alter body perception for health and well-being. Following a Research through Design process drawing from soma design, [25] and a co-design methodological approach, we invited professional dancers as expert participants and co-designers. Dancers participated in two home studies and two workshops involving somatic and material explorations. Besides dancers being one of the target groups of our project, we believed that their somatic connoisseurship [78] and their unique relationship to body perception and movement (such as their proprioceptive acuity [35] and bodily control [7]) could support nuanced explorations of somatic design materials.

We contribute an approach to explore the design space of body perception alterations fostered by sensory technologies. This approach involves, first, engaging participants in accessing, expressing, and sharing their body sensations, making them actionable for the design process and to others. Second, engaging in deep and rich somatic explorations of materials with diverse sensory stimuli, to explore how they could reduce, intensify, transform, or heighten awareness of their sensations. Third, the approach involves leveraging insights to collaboratively design concepts for future technologies that could alter body perception. In addition to the overall approach, we contribute:

- Experiential facets of body sensations that are important to take into account in design.
- Various movement and sensory stimuli potentials to alter body sensations.
- Methodological knowledge in the form of concrete design methods and practical strategies for incorporating body sensations into the design process.
- A collection of design concepts that show the generative capacity of our approach and can spark inspiration for future technology development.

Our work offers a resource for researchers in multiple body-centric communities interested in sensory technologies, body perception alterations, and working with body sensations as design material, such as multisensory HCI (e.g. [11, 62, 95, 120]), soma design (e.g. [30, 33]), human-computer integration [58, 89], embodied interaction (e.g. [59, 93, 121]), and particular application domains (e.g. sports, games, rehabilitation [56, 57, 85, 117]).

2 BACKGROUND

We draw from recent integrative research on body sensations [42, 52, 97], which considers evolutionary, psychological and neuroscientific perspectives, to conceptualize body perception and body

sensations in our work. We review related HCI research working with body sensations as design material.

2.1 Theoretical Underpinnings

Body perception is a complex and multifaceted phenomena, involving various bodily multisensory signals as well as sociocultural and personal experiences [42, 52, 97]. It encompasses intimately interrelated facets, such as perceptions of one's body's *configuration* and *motor capabilities* [45, 54]), *body appearance* (e.g. shape and size [20, 53]), and *sensations* that are localized or felt in the body, regardless of their sensory origin ([42], pg.13), and of which people can be aware [19]. These various facets are not experientially isolated constructs [44]. They are part of our body experience constituted as an integrated whole, in which sensations, emotions, movements, thoughts, sociocultural interactions and other manifestations intertwine and dynamically co-shape each other [1, 17, 23, 42, 44, 70, 81], impacting people's motor, emotional, and social functioning [1, 17, 23, 70, 81]. However, articulating manifestations of our body experience in linguistic constructs (e.g. terms such as sensation, emotion, memory, etc.) enables us to examine the complexity of our body experiences and their mutual co-constitution [42, 73]. Here, we propose that centering the design inquiry in body sensations felt in the body can help people identify, articulate and explore in depth the interplay between sensory stimuli and alterations in their holistic body perception.

2.1.1 Body Sensations. Body sensations encompass a wide range of felt experiences related to one's body. Physiologically, they are experienced through two body systems related to their perception and regulation [43]: *homeostatic*, concerning internal physiological states and processes (e.g. thermosensation, visceral pain, muscle fatigue, nausea, and hunger [18]), and *somatosensory*, concerning processing sensory input related to body-environment relation (including e.g. proprioceptive [23, 54] and vestibular signals, externally induced pain, or tactile information). While people can feel sensations in specific body areas (e.g. knee pain), sometimes sensations are diffuse and felt spread across the body (e.g. cold when the body temperature drops) [18]. Body sensations are often subject to subjective appraisal [42]. That is, people might experience them as positive, desirable, pleasant, etc., or as negative, or unfavourable. This appraisal is in turn shaped by individual and sociocultural influences (e.g. memories, health expectations, prior experiences, sociocultural norms and body ideals [104]), and therefore changes across cultures and even groups of people [42, 97, 114]. Finally, how we experience our body sensations changes over time, depending on the actual body and its physiological changes, but also on perceived sensory information, which shapes our body experience [3, 5]. This means that body sensations are malleable, and can be shaped by sensory information that does not originate in the body [42]. This opens for the potential of sensory stimuli to transform people's perception of their own body [114] in a holistic way: impacting the feelings about body, movement and emotions, and where the sensory stimuli's evocative power is crucial (ibid.).

2.2 Related Works

Multisensory research in HCI and cognitive neuroscience has long studied sensory technology to alter body perception (e.g., [46, 48, 62,

85, 100, 120]). This community has yielded multiple explorations on the impact of different sensory feedback on perception [87], e.g. tapping sounds inducing illusions of having a longer arm [98, 101, 102]; creaky sounds making individuals feel stiffer [48, 87], haptic feedback leading to perceptual illusions of phantom limbs [9, 106], and visual feedback in VR fostering perceived changes in body weight [68], and size [94, 118]. These insights have been explored in different contexts, such as sports, dance, motor learning, health and rehabilitation (e.g. [12, 15, 28, 62, 74, 77, 80]). Relatedly, Human-Computer Integration works propose to integrate devices directly into the human body to alter perception [39, 58, 89, 125].

Other relevant related works focus on body sensations. These can be found in particular application domains such as sports (e.g. [4, 55, 86, 124]), or body-centric games (e.g. [13, 57]). Most of these works seek instrumental goals through the introduction of sensory technology [109, 113]. Some aim to increase people's awareness of their motor capabilities and performance e.g. [88, 116]. Others focus on inducing felt sensations to e.g. improve instructions through recreating the sensation of being pulled and pushed during snowboarding [86], or to foster competition in a game where players can induce sensations of imbalance in others [57]. However, these works do not elaborate on how their focus on body sensations shapes their design process, nor shape the body experience beyond predefined goals (e.g. improve instruction and performance, fun and play).

In these communities, works are typically hypothesis-driven or inspired, with a focus on *evaluating* the effects of sensory actuation on body perception. Yet, there is less emphasis on early and in-depth explorations of its potential to foster meaningful alterations. We suggest that new methodological approaches may be necessary to address this gap. For that, we draw from soma design - a methodology that centers on the body as design material.

2.3 Design as the Orchestration of Various Design Materials

We draw from soma design works to approach body sensations as design material. Soma design [30] foregrounds the deepening of our bodily and aesthetic appreciation, and proposes a deep, felt, subjective and somatic engagement with sociodigital materials to shape meaningful interactive experiences that highlight the interconnectedness of sensations, feelings, emotions, and values [65, 90]. In soma design, *designing* is viewed as an orchestration of various design elements [30], bringing together people, interactive artifacts, and bodily, material, and cultural aspects.

We consider sensations as design material as articulated by Höök [30], (p.16): *we are designing with a sociodigital material, our own somas [...] are also a design material of sorts. [...] our bodies and our subjective experiences, feelings, values, meaning-making, and movement-based engagements are altered by the design process.* Further, we work not only with somatic elements, but also physical objects: we engage in deep somatic explorations of sensory stimuli elicited by such objects [49, 113]. The materiality of body sensations differs from the materiality of objects [26]: they might be less tangible, and some sensations can be induced through physical objects - as we will illustrate throughout our empirics. Our work focuses on the intersection of somatic elements and objects' materiality co-shaping each other [30, 66, 113].

Multiple soma design works (e.g. [22, 31, 33, 36, 49, 64, 65, 107, 108]) have focused on body sensations as design material to shape and be shaped through somatic engagement with other design materials. For example, exploring sensations of balance [31, 50], or pelvic floor tilting [90] have shaped full design processes. Most soma design works strongly emphasize and foreground body awareness and self-discovery (e.g. [33, 36, 90–92, 107]). In this paper, we contribute to, and expand, these works by exploring how centering on body sensations as design material can not only deepen awareness of the body but also *alter* body perception in significant ways.

3 METHODOLOGY AND METHODS

This paper is part of a larger project, BODYinTRANSIT, which seeks to develop novel wearables to improve self-body perception in people prone to body concerns (i.e. unfavourable appraisals on their body). Our team is multidisciplinary, including interaction designers, soma designers, HCI researchers, cognitive neuroscientists and performance artists. This study constituted early efforts within the project to understand how dancers (one of the targeted populations) perceived their body and to derive design ideas for prototypes.

We adopted a Research through Design approach [25], a methodology that utilizes design artifacts and methods to explore situations and challenges and generate design ideas. We also employed a co-design approach [84]. Potential participants were recruited through the lab's dance networks. They had to be professional dancers or enrolled in advanced dance programs. Due to BODYinTRANSIT's focus, we used the Multidimensional Body-Self Relations Questionnaire [8] to select participants susceptible to body concerns, which in dancers often emerge from the pressure of achieving peak physical performance while conforming to an ideal body image ([67]). Our study centered on investigating body sensations and did not address body concerns, but selecting participants with these traits allows us to potentially utilize insights in future studies in the project. Twelve participants (8 women and 4 men), aged 18 to 46 ($M=28.16$, $SD=7.6$), joined the study. Eight had over 7 years of professional dance experience, three had 1 to 2 years. All were pursuing or had completed graduate degrees in dance. Ten were trained in contemporary dance, one in classical dance, and one in improvisation dance. Nine participated in all the activities.

The study involved sensitization and ideation phases [41]. These phases incorporated various activities, such as home exercises and workshops. The study took place over a 3,5 month period. Figure 1 provides an overview of the study, showing the activities that form the empirical base of this study that we explain next.

3.1 Sensitizing

The sensitizing phase intended for participants to articulate meaningful body sensations that they felt in their everyday life - with the aim to share it with the design team and other participants. It also intended to introduce participants to working with design materials (i.e. movement and sensory stimuli, such as haptic and sound) as sensitization to the upcoming design ideation phase.

3.1.1 Home Exercise 1: Questionnaire of Somatic Perceptions and Sensations. In the first home exercise (henceforth: HE1), participants engaged in an individual inquiry at home for two weeks, focusing on felt sensations that they experienced in their everyday

Figure 1: A visualization of the phases and activities that form the empirical basis of our study.

life. We encouraged participants to focus on positive and negative sensations that they experienced throughout the day as a way to identify salient experiences. Participants completed an online questionnaire with at least 3 positive and 3 negative sensations. Inspired by theories on body sensations [27], we asked for a general description of a felt sensation and its relation to their motor, emotional and social experience. We also added relevant questions, e.g. when the sensation was felt, its body location, how long it lasted, etc.

3.1.2 Workshop 1: Somatic Walkthrough and Sensory Bodystorming. The first workshop (henceforth: WS1) lasted about 4 hours. We had 12 participants and 7 facilitators: 5 design researchers and 2 choreographers (lab collaborators), to aid us in co-organizing warming-up activities and help participants during somatic explorations.

The workshop was video recorded. We wanted participants to first, explore first-hand some of the sensations they had shared with us. For that, participants engaged in a **somatic walkthrough**, an activity we devised to allow participants to 1) reconnect with the sensations they had shared with us, and 2) share with other participants, verbally and somatically, their body sensations, akin to a walkthrough through the sensations (e.g. what it was, where it was felt, how it affected them). Others were encouraged to integrate this information into their own somatic experiences, to relate to the sensation from a first-person perspective. Participants were divided into smaller groups to create a more intimate space (4 groups of 3, plus a facilitator). Participants selected one or two questionnaire responses (which we had printed for each participant) that they wanted to share with the rest. One by one, we invited them to briefly introduce their sensation and then try to reconnect somatically with it by e.g. moving in a way that would allow them to feel (or reminiscence aspects of) it again. Others were encouraged to creatively appropriate such expression, integrating it into their own somatic understanding through movement exploration in their own interpretation. We facilitators employed prompts drawing from Laban's movement qualities [75] (e.g. shape and direction in physical space, speed, continuity and smoothness, weight of a movement) to prompt creative divergences in their explorations. Finally, we debriefed together what occurred.

In the second activity, a **sensory bodystorming** [113], we wanted participants to explore how different movements and sensory stimuli could influence their sensations. We brought a *bodystorming basket* [119], a collection of objects with diverse tangible and sound properties, that we had curated for their potential of eliciting different sensory stimuli (Figure 2.a). Individually, participants focused on one of the sensations they had explored during the somatic walkthrough and were encouraged to explore if, through haptic or sound stimuli, they could influence it. As generative prompts, we gave participants four verbs (i.e. intensify, reduce, bring awareness, transform) to open up the design space in regards to what they could attempt to do with their body sensations through design. However, we also gave them the option to explore other action verbs, if they wanted. Participants selected an object from the available pool, and somatically explored if, and how, it would influence their felt sensations. They were encouraged to try various objects and to change action verbs as they wanted. We facilitators moved among them, asking them from time to time to verbalize what they were doing to document it on camera. This activity helped bridge the sensitizing and the upcoming ideation.

3.2 Ideation

This phase focused on exploring how sensations could be altered through the somatic engagement with materials, and on generating design concepts.

3.2.1 Home Exercise 2: Body Maps and Ideation. In the second home exercise (henceforth: HE2), we gave the participants printed A4 sheets to help them come up with seed design ideas at home (Fig. 2.b). On the left, the sheets included a body map and guiding questions, intended to help participants articulate body sensations, what they would like to do with it in design, and how they envision it could impact them. On the right, participants were instructed to imagine a future technology that could help them achieve their aims on the left. We wanted them to be as creative and unconstrained as possible, so we provided clear instructions to not worry about costs or feasibility. Participants engaged in individual ideation at home for two weeks. We asked them to come up with at least 5 distinct

Figure 2: Examples of different methodological considerations. a) Bodystorming Basket: a mix of materials we brought to the workshops for ideation. b) Sheets that participants took home during the second home exercise, also in Supplementary Material. c) Snippet from the diagrams created from the video analysis, in this case of the sensory bodystorming activity.

design ideas and share them with us prior to the next workshop via email (i.e. taking a picture of the sheets, or scanning them).

3.2.2 Workshop 2: Experiencing Ideas and Video Prototyping. The second workshop (henceforth: WS2) was run twice due to scheduling conflicts among participants. Four participants participated on the first day, and five on the second. Each lasted 3 hours and was video recorded. The aim was for participants to experience and low-fi prototype one of the ideas they had shared in HE2. Six facilitators (5 researchers, a choreographer) helped with prototyping.

Experiencing Ideas. In the first activity, **experiencing ideas**, akin to the somatic walkthrough, participants were divided into groups of two or three, each group having one or two facilitators. Each group selected a couple of ideas (which we had printed) that they wanted to explore and then shared them with the others. Then they engaged in a short somatic walkthrough, to sensitize themselves to the sensation at focus. Next, taking turns, participants described their idea for a wearable technology that could influence their chosen sensation. Collectively, participants engaged in an embodied sketching [59] activity, and used various objects from the bodystorming basket to experiment with different possible ways of simulating the effects of this imagined technology. Participants sketched very low-fi artefacts and helped the participant who originated the idea to experience first-hand how their sensations were being influenced (e.g. by faking the technology’s interactivity). Next, other participants in the group experienced the idea first-hand too, to provide additional insights and refinements. Participants talked aloud throughout the exercise, signalling what they were feeling, what worked well, and what would need to be changed. Participants engaged collective decision-making. Through this iterative process, ideas were polished until a design concept was articulated.

Video Prototyping. In the second part of WS2, we helped participants finish building a low-fidelity prototype of their idea, with emphasis put on illustrating its interactivity with the help of their team. The objective was to present this prototype in the context of a **video prototype**: a short performance (3 minutes max.), where they would show their initial sensation and the impact it had on them, their wearable technology and its interaction, and the effects that it would have on the initial sensation. For the performance, our choreographer-facilitator acted as a TV presenter who invited and interviewed the participants as creators of technologies showcasing their “inventions”. Each dancer (and their team, if needed) enacted

in this context their resulting ideas to the rest of the audience participants. After this workshop, we sent out a short final online questionnaire, asking participants about their study experiences.

3.3 Data Analysis

Our work involved different analyses on different data sources, although all were inspired by reflexive approaches to coding [10] that combine deductive and inductive analysis to find conceptually related codes and themes. HE1 questionnaire responses were initially open-coded by the 1st author, combining inductive and deductive approaches. Theoretical concepts from the literature informed the initial coding, refined collaboratively with the last author over two sessions to establish final groupings. Interviews underwent similar analysis by the 1st author, with input from others. Video data from WS1 and WS2 were primarily analyzed using video analysis [29] and interaction analysis [37] by the 2nd and 3rd authors, with supervision from the 1st author. Diagrams were created to visualize e.g. sensations at focus, actions and interactions, effects of the interactions, as well as their evolution (Figure 2.c). The 1st author reviewed the analysis, adding further detail from raw data. The 3rd author, supervised by the 1st, translated insights into spreadsheets to identify patterns (e.g. cross-tabulating the use of different haptic and sound qualities with the effects on the sensations participants had experienced). The resulting tables were extensively discussed and refined by the 1st and 3rd authors, with input from the last author. This process yielded insights presented in Section 4.2. We also selected empirical examples from the video data to illustrate how people engaged in the varied activities of our approach.

4 RESULTS

We group our empirical findings into key considerations of our approach - which centers on body sensations as design material that can help people identify, articulate and explore in depth interesting interplays between sensory stimuli and body perception alterations. First, we show that our sensitizing activities helped participants explore in depth and articulate rich facets of their felt body sensations. To do so, we show insights on three facets of body sensations resulting from our analysis, and bring an illustrative example on how people shared body sensations with others. Second, we show how participants engaged in somatic explorations of simple materials with varied sensory stimuli to explore how they influenced their sensations. To do so, we bring an illustrative example on how people shared body sensations with others and a collection

of movement and sensory potentials identified through our analysis. Third, we show how participants collectively leveraged insights and sketched concepts for future technologies, bringing another illustrative example of the design process behind one such concept, and showing the collection of resulting ideas.

4.1 Sensitizing Participants to Body Sensations and Making Them Available for Design

4.1.1 Facets of Body Sensations. When considering body sensations as design material, it is important to recognize their diverse types and emergence, how they are shaped by individual and sociocultural factors [19, 27, 53, 54, 105], and understand how they impact participants and interrelate with other aspects of body perception. The first home exercise (HE1) helped participants focus on, and pinpoint, interesting body experiences emerging around a body sensation that they felt in their everyday life. We received 65 questionnaire responses. Drawing inspiration from prior soma design work [24], we here use lenses to zoom into facets of our somatic experience. We employ three lenses to structure the results of the questionnaire's analysis: 1) sensation type, 2) emergence and temporality, 3) interrelation with, and impact on, other aspects of the body experience. Empirically, we present few detailed examples of participants' questionnaire responses showing the interconnection of sensations with other experiential aspects of body experience. We also present a coarser characterization to highlight the breadth of reported sensations. This a subsection that may be particularly relevant to those aiming to focus on body sensations but not yet acquainted with their experiential facets.

1) Type. Participants mostly focused on sensations primarily felt in the upper body (chest, trunk, arms) or throughout the entire body. As per instruction, sensations were reported as either positive or negative. Some reported sensations related to **body appearance**, e.g. body weight and size. For example, P5 reported in a questionnaire response feelings of heaviness in her trunk and legs when she did not accomplish particular pirouettes or "tricks" during training. In those moments, she reported that the sensation of heaviness led her to believe that she would not be able to perform the tricks, which in turn sometimes made her abandon the training session altogether. She also reported that sometimes, when experiencing such heaviness, she engaged in a conscious attempt to stop associating agility with body weight. Other participants reported other body appearance-related sensations, such as feeling thin when comparing oneself to others (P7), feeling big during movements (P1), or bloating while zipping pants (P4).

Participants also felt sensations that related to **body capabilities**, such as strength, agility, and so forth. For example, P1 reported feelings of strength in his arms after moving his upper limbs during training. He reported this sensation to last for several days, in which it made him feel more beautiful and sexy and wanting to show off that part of his body because he derived pleasure when others commented on his strong arms. Other capability-related sensations reported included agility during post-physical activity (P2), and feeling a good physical condition (P1). Negative sensations encompassed weakness when lifting weights (P1), excessive flexibility (P7) or lack of coordination (P10) during training, reduced muscle tone due to ageing (P10), and rigidity in unfamiliar dance styles

(P10). Finally, participants also reported other sensations, such as feeling energy during training (P4, P10), or stomach tingling from compliments (P11). Negative sensations included physical fatigue (P2, P3, P6, P7, P9, P10), pain (P2, P2, P9, P10), or widespread muscle tension (P8).

2) Emergence and Temporality. An important characteristic of body sensations is their variability in regard to when participants felt that their sensations emerged and the time that they lasted, often influenced by contextual and individual factors. In our study, we found that positive self-perceptions, like being satisfied with the own body, were experientially linked to a sensation of increased energy. For example, P8 reported that sometimes, when she received compliments from her teacher or colleagues on her performance, she would feel accepted, valid and proud of herself. She would often experience a widespread sensation of energy in her body, that could sometimes last for days. When experiencing this sensation, she would feel motivated to engage to a greater extent with her training. Conversely, negative self-comparisons were linked to fostering negative sensations, such as a widespread thinness when comparing oneself to others (P7). Other reported reasons related to movement and training, e.g. feeling muscle fatigue (P6) and pain (P10) during training, or agile and strong for hours afterwards (P3). For P11, prolonged inactivity led to a heavy feeling in the legs, and improper execution of movements sometimes was connected to feelings of physical discomfort (P4).

3) Impact. Body sensations are intertwined with other aspects of people's body experience, impacting people's motor, emotional, and social functioning [42]. Some participants reported that their sensations strongly impacted their **emotions**. Often, what they deemed negative sensations generally led to emotions that they also deemed negative, and vice versa. For example, P1 felt big during certain moments of his practice, which in turn made him feel powerful and motivated. In contrast, a "feeling big" sensation made P4 feel uncomfortable, as she associated this sensation with being too fat for her dance practice. When experiencing this sensation, P4 felt blocked and distant from herself and others. Others also connected weight-related sensations to strong emotional responses, such as helplessness (P9), and self-rejection (P11). Sensations related to body capabilities were also often connected to emotions. For example, P12 often experienced euphoria and happiness when he felt his muscles to have strength during training (P12). Others connected feeling weakness to being sad (P11); feeling tired to losing motivation to do things (P1), or feeling guilty for not being in a better shape (P3). Pain led to emotional exhaustion from having to deal with it constantly (P10) and irritability (P2).

Participants felt that their sensations shaped *how they moved*. For example, in P1's previous example, feeling big, motivated and powerful made him also more daring: he would engage in exploring movements that were new for him, or that he did not feel so confident performing. Others connected feeling light to calmer movements (P4). Some participants reported feeling strength promoted ample (P10), energized (P3) or powerful (P4) movements. Others connected rigidity to limited, less natural movements (P10). Pain made some reduce their movement range (P9).

Some participants reported that their sensations strongly shaped their *social interactions*. P4 described feeling bloated in her lower belly while zipping her pants. This sensation often caused her

Figure 3: Snippets of P3, P5 and P10's movement exploration of tension in the somatic walkthrough activity.

discomfort and prompted her to try to conceal this area during training. Despite this, she acknowledged making a conscious effort to accept the variability in her body's appearance and sensations from day to day. Others reported that feeling agile improved their mood when interacting with others (P2). P4's confidence in social situations was increased when feeling strength, while a low muscle tone led P10 to feel the need to explain her physical condition to others. P10 reported that experiencing pain caused her to distance herself from her peers, and P7 connected feeling tired to focusing more on herself at the expense of social interactions. Finally, some participants connected their sensations to their perceived body image. For example, the previous example of P1's feeling beautiful and sexy when he experienced strength. P5's reported an increase in her self-esteem also when experiencing strength. Feeling heavy led P8 to disconnect from her body image, and caused P5 to judge herself. Lastly, P2's reported that his self-esteem was negatively impacted when feeling tired.

Next, we describe how participants shared such personal experiences with others, sensitizing others to their body experience and making sensations available to design.

4.1.2 Sharing Body Sensations with Others. The Somatic Walkthrough in WS1 proved to be a meaningful exercise to help participants share their body sensations somatically with other participants and the research team, making them available for design. To illustrate how participants did so, we provide a detailed example from an exploration of the sensation of tension. P10 chose to share with P3, P5 and us a sensation of tension around her right clavicle: *I have a chronic lesion in the clavicle, and hence a sensation of tension, of muscle blockage, that irradiates to different areas. This sensation upsets me [...] and brings me a need to try to open, to expand [the area], but I always have something that pulls me back inwards* (Figure 3.a). The facilitator encouraged them to explore somatically this duality of opening up the muscles and inevitably pulling back. They each explored this sensation in their own movement styles for about three minutes. P10 noted that her sensation increased and realized she was protecting that area, not engaging her right shoulder as much. P3, who did not have a lesion, enjoyed the sensations of tension and relaxation. The facilitator provided prompts to change their movement exploration. The first prompt was to feel the muscle sensation radiating down the back and legs, leading to changes in their posture and less movement in their lower limbs (Fig. 3.b). They were also encouraged to slow down their movement, resulting in slow, expansive arm movements (Fig.3.c), and then to experiment with speed changes. P5 said her tension increased with slow opening and quick pull-back movements, akin to a rubber band. The opposite did not create tension.

After this exploration, P10 elaborated on the impact of the sensation on her: *It stresses me, thinking and worrying about that area all the time, trying to not be in pain, thinking that I can't lift up this person [in certain dance moves], I can't lean on this side, I can't use this arm. [...] It makes me feel like I am more limited, it brings me to slower, stiller movements.* Participants were encouraged to further explore the sensation of slow, still movement, moving in small, controlled movements. The facilitator encouraged them to explore how extending this shoulder's stillness to their entire body would feel. P10 enjoyed these explorations because they freed her from the requirement to move the shoulder that she usually feels in her profession. She felt her tension *transform into something positive [...] I do not need to do anything with it, so I relax* (P10). Conversely, P3 felt overwhelmed and restricted from her usual broad movements in that body area. For P4, it evoked memories of past injuries but presented a creative challenge to explore the emerging possibilities when moving only a few body parts.

Through the somatic walkthrough exercise, participants could reconnect with the sensations they had shared in the questionnaire, and share with other participants, verbally and somatically, their body sensations. Others were encouraged to integrate this information into their own somatic experiences, to relate to the sensation from a first-person perspective. This resulted in a shared experience that they would later build upon during the design process.

4.2 Shaping Body Sensations through Movement and Sensory Stimuli

In the previous section's empirical example, we showed that in the somatic walkthrough participants also explored how different movement qualities affected their body sensations. In the sensory bodystorming (WS1) and the embodied sketching (WS2) activities, participants also engaged in somatic and material explorations of how different movement qualities and sensory stimuli shaped their sensations. For example, following P10's injury example in the previous section, P10 used haptic stimuli to bring awareness to her shoulder tension during the sensory bodystorming. She began by using a small plastic scratching rake with pointy ends that contained tiny balls, conducting a mostly static exploration with closed eyes (Figure 4.a). She applied short but intense bouts of pressure to different points on her clavicle and neck (Fig. 4.b). She noted the richness of information she derived from each individual point: *There are some points of pain, but in others, I do not feel anything. I become aware of where the tension and pain are exactly, and that they are not as widespread as I thought.* Next, she gently dragged the rake from her upper back to the clavicle in a slow, continuous motion (Fig. 4.c), which fostered a general stretch and muscular expansion,

Figure 4: Snippets of P10's sensory exploration of tension in the sensory bodystorming activity.

reducing tension overall but not at specific points. She experienced similar effects in other body areas (Fig. 4.d) and concluded that sustained pressure applied at various points with slow movements brought awareness to her tension, while a gentle dragging helped reduce tension. Wanting to experience pressure without applying it herself, she tried using a dumbbell on her leg (Fig. 4.e), but it was too light and rigid. However, when she used it on smaller and more sensitive body areas, i.e. her arm and shoulder (Fig. 4.f), she felt the pressure better, which brought awareness to her tension.

These somatic engagements with sensations, movement and sensory stimuli resulted in different movement and sensory potentials to alter body perception - through intensifying, reducing, bring awareness or transforming their body sensations. No participant decided to explore other action verbs beyond the ones we provided. Such actions were not always occurring in isolation (e.g. bringing awareness and intensifying often happened jointly). Rather, they allowed participants to articulate the main effects they experienced. Participants' explorations were slow and extensive, and their articulations and insights rich. These movement and sensory potentials were all felt in real time by the participants during the workshop explorations, rather than e.g. "learned" through their dancing practice. Next, we report on various potentials we identified. As in prior works [49], we present them as an initial design space populated by interesting potentials that should be explored, validated and expanded in future work.

4.2.1 Movement Potentials. Through the analysis of all the explorations, we found reoccurring movement potentials.

Slowing down movement and movement weight intensifies sensations. Most of the participants expressed that slowing down their movement intensified their sensations, for example, P4's overall bodily heaviness when moving extremely slow (Figure 5.a). Similarly, roughly half of the participants noted that movement weight also intensified their sensations. Lighter movements heightened positive sensations, e.g. P7 and P6 found that lighter movements intensified their sensation of chest relaxation became. Conversely, heavy movements appeared to intensify negative sensations, as evidenced by P2 (Fig. 5.b) and P9, whose feelings of pressure were heightened during heavy movements.

Spatial changes in movement transforms sensations. All participants who explored expansive movements in space (e.g. reaching out more, expanding their kinesphere [14] reported a transformation in their sensations and appraisals. For example, P5 initially experienced a positive undulating sensation, which turned into stiffness when she made ample movements. Conversely, P3 and P10, who were feeling chest pressure, felt a sensation of release as their movements expanded, because they felt less constrained and

free to move (Fig. 5.c). Relatedly, few participants mentioned that other movement changes in space (e.g. contraction, or translation) also altered their sensations, often to positive ones.

Movement fluidity intensifies and transforms sensations. Most participants found that when their movements became less continuous and more shaky, their negative sensations were intensified, and positive ones turned negative. For example, P10 experienced increased chest pressure with jerkier movements, while P5's undulating movement sensation transformed into stiffness. Conversely, fluid movements had the opposite effect, turning negative sensations into positive ones, e.g. P3, P5 and P10 felt chest pressure transform to relaxation with fluid movements (Fig. 5.d).

4.2.2 Sensory Stimuli Potentials. Through the analysis of all the explorations, we also found reoccurring sensory potentials. These potentials emerged in the context of a somatic exploration. Thus, they are intertwined with specific movements.

Haptic: Pressure brings awareness to sensations. Most participants reported that applying pressure to their body brought their awareness to their sensations. For example, P4 brought awareness to the heaviness in her trunk with a small dumbbell, which increased her felt weight (Fig. 5.e). For few participants, however, pressure served to also reduce the felt sensations, in particular those that were experienced as negative, such as anguish.

Haptic: Haptic stimuli reduces sensations or brings awareness to them. Most participants primarily focused on the haptic properties of objects to reduce or increase attention to sensations. For example, P11's muscular tension was reduced when she held a wool ball tight to her chest: its warm temperature helped her to alleviate the pressure and that its smooth and soft texture helped her to relax.

Haptic: Temperature brings awareness to sensations. Most participants found that warmth brought awareness to their sensations, e.g. P11 became more aware of the pain in her foot when she employed a piece of fabric wrapped around a roller to roll her foot's sole because the fabric was hot (Fig. 5.f). To some, warm stimuli also intensified sensations, particularly those experienced as positive. In contrast, few participants found that cold stimuli transformed their sensations (e.g. from heaviness felt in the legs to discomfort).

Haptic: Slow contact with stimuli reduces sensations. Most participants reported that slowly moving an object throughout their body reduced their negative sensations, e.g. P10 decreased her tension by slowly dragging the racket. In contrast, some participants reported that touching themselves with objects in a fast manner made them feel their negative sensations (e.g. anguish, tension) more intensely.

Haptic: The texture of objects transforms sensations. A few participants mentioned that textures played a role in how they perceived

Figure 5: Snippets illustrating different movement, haptic and sound potentials to shape sensations.

themselves. A smooth surface touching the legs rhythmically transformed one participant’s sensation of heaviness to one of fluidity. Similarly, an elastic texture transformed another participant’s sensation of heaviness into one of strength when engaging with it. In contrast, a few participants said that rough textures (such as spikes) either intensified or reduced their sensations.

Sound: *Sound stimuli intensifies sensations.* In overall, participants predominantly utilized objects that produced auditory stimuli when they sought to intensify a sensation. For instance, P1 reported that the sound that the brush made when he caressed its plastic spikes (e.g. a hoop-and-loop fastener being separated) evoked imagery of muscle tearing or ripping, especially when he did it slowly. This intensified the pain that he was feeling in his abs (Fig. 5.g).

Sound: *Slow tempo and low pitch intensify negative sensations* Some participants experienced that a slow tempo intensified negative sensations. For example, P11 experienced that her perceived brain fog was intensified when she produced a slow-paced sound with a wooden rattle and synchronized her movements with it (Fig. 5.h). With a faster tempo, her brain fog dissipated and she felt energized instead. Relatedly, low-pitch sounds intensified sensations of pain and heaviness. For example, P4 heaviness increased in her body with the low-pitched sounds of a drum being struck with a wooden stick (Fig. 5.i), which made her feel as being pressed down.

Sound: *Low volume reduces negative sensations, high volume increases them.* Several participants reported that playing a sound in a low volume help them reduce negative sensations (e.g. anguish). In contrast, high volume increased them, e.g. P2’s pain was intensified when he played a loud, discrete noise with a wooden box.

Sound: *Positioning of the sound intensifies or reduces sensations.* All participants but one felt that their relative positioning to the sound source intensified or reduced their sensations. For example, P5, using a metal cube being hit with a metal stick, noted that when she faced the sound directly, her sensation of heaviness in the thighs intensified (Fig. 5.j). Yet, the sensation was reduced when she heard the sound behind her body (Fig. 5.i). Others noted that when the sound was above them, it intensified sensations because it felt close to their head; if it originated from their lower extremities, it reduced them as it seemed distant.

4.3 Generating Design Concepts

We describe how participants’ somatic engagement with sensory inputs was leveraged to collaboratively sketch, prototype, experience and refine design concepts for future sensory technology to alter body perception. We present a collection of design concepts to show the generative capacity of our approach and the type of ideas that were created.

WS1 (3.1.2) sensitized dancers to working with body sensations alongside other design materials. Through movement and sensory exploration, they discovered the potential of shaping their relationship with these sensations through design. Thus, in HE2 (3.2.1), they were able to generate 45 unique design ideas by engaging in similar explorations at home: focusing on a specific body sensation and experimenting with movement and sensory potentials that would intensify, reduce, transform or bring awareness to them. The sensations on which they focused in this exercise covered a wide range, from negative (e.g., rigidity, muscle weakness) to positive (e.g., flexibility, tingling), with most participants aiming to reduce or transform the former and intensify the latter. Haptic stimuli were favoured in most ideas. For instance, P4 aimed to bring awareness to her body’s balance and proprioception. At home, she experimented with a water-filled bottle that remained level regardless of her movements. This inspired in her the concept of a suit with embedded pipes, allowing water to flow in response to her movements and thus bringing awareness to her balance and proprioception (Figure 6.a). In contrast, only a few ideas incorporated sound stimuli, such as P5’s, which aimed to intensify her sensation of flowing body movements. Inspired by the sound of running water, she envisioned a wearable earpiece that would sonify her movements with water-like sounds. Through this exercise, we generated design ideas that were highly individualized, as participants envisioned designs for very personal and intimate somatic experiences.

In WS2, participants selected one or two of their design ideas and collaborated in small groups to experience them first-hand using available crafting materials. To illustrate this process, we use P4’s example of the suit with water-filled pipes for increasing proprioception and balance. This idea builds on considerations that P4 shared already in HE1 (3.1.1), that an increased sense of proprioception and balance are sensations that impacted her in positive

Figure 6: Design of a suit inspired by the sound of water in response to her movements. a) First water suit drawing at home. b) Somatic walkthrough of the sensation of balance. c) Participants crafting the design idea with the available material. d) Participant exploring variations of the idea, e.g. a water bottle to her chest, cardboard with marbles on her leg. e) Sharing body experience with others.

ways (e.g. making her feel accomplished, or worthy). In WS2, akin to the somatic walkthrough exercise in WS1, P4 shared verbally and somatically her sensation of balance and increased proprioception with others (Fig.6.b), and they all engaged in exploring the sensations individually. Next, P4 explained her design concept and participants helped her experience it using materials. Initially, they attempted to fill clown balloons with water, but that proved challenging. They creatively devised alternatives to replicate the weight and flow of water, such as filling corrugated tubes with marbles and beans and attaching them to P4's arm (Fig. 6.c). As P4 moved, she found this setup brought more awareness to her balance, especially when she listened to the sounds produced by the marbles. Desiring to experiment further with the weight and sound of real water, participants affixed a half-full water bottle to her chest (Fig. 6.d). After moving with this addition, P4 appreciated the genuine water experience, but preferred the corrugated tubes' flexibility, girth and length which made the sound and weight react more accurately to her movements: as the marbles took longer to reach the extremes of the tube, when she did ample movements she kept experiencing feedback throughout. Participants tried attaching a cardboard tube filled with marbles to P4's leg, but its rigidity impeded her movements, so they abandoned the idea. Other participants also tried out P4's idea on themselves (Fig. 6.e). This collective exploration contributed to sediment the concept, incorporating additional insights. For instance, P2 observed an improvement in his sense of balance with it, as well as an increased proprioception. Further, P5 suggested that instead of the marbles abruptly stopping when reaching the tube's end, extending the sound longer would help her keep feeling balance.

During these explorations, each participant refined and prototyped their ideas collaboratively in low-fi mock-ups. They also documented them through video prototypes. This resulted in 9 distinct ideas (Figure 7). Most ideas focused on negative sensations, wanting to reduce, transform or bring awareness to them. Two focused on balance, either to bring awareness to it or intensify it. Most ideas involved wearables, with some also featuring interactive installations. We briefly describe each idea to give a sense of the sketched design concepts. Details of each can be found in the Supplementary.

a) Soothing Dress. (P9) Shape-changing clothing that leverages different touch interactions to intensify negative sensations (e.g.

anxiety) and later transforms them into a sensation of calmness, or being relieved and relaxed.

b) Tension-Less. (P5) A wearable that detects muscle tension, making a person feel rigid, frustrated and incapable during dancing. It uses heat, a low sound of running water and gentle pressure (building on sensory potentials, 4.2.2) to reduce tension and transform it to a sensation of fluidity, leaving the person liberated and more mobile.

c) Apnea. (P7). A wearable bringing awareness to breathing apneas when dancing by providing resistance to movements, in feedback loops. Through this, the person becomes more aware of their body movements and apneas, transforming rigid movements into fluid ones, increasing proprioception.

d) Massaging Pants. (P3). Interactive pants with inflatable technology to transform through pressure feelings of heaviness and tiredness to feelings of calm and rest.

e) Power Suit. (P10). A body suit that fosters, or intensifies, feelings of muscle power, intensity and resistance through adjustable resistances making it difficult to move. It transforms those feelings into lightness once removed.

f) Spatial Center of Gravity. (P1). An interactive installation that brings awareness to how a dancers' body's center of gravity relates to the space via elastic textiles that generate tension as the dancer moves.

g) The Weight of Tiredness. (P2). A wearable (exemplified through a glove) with interactive weights that becomes heavier as you become tired. It helps the wearer become aware on their own tiredness and energy levels - through a felt sensation of how even mundane tasks (e.g. grabbing a cup) transform to effortful movements when tired.

h) Balance Soundscape (P6). A 3D sound installation to engage in explorations of balance. It intensifies and brings awareness to balance through movement sonification: the soundscape reacts to subtle changes in body balance, triggering a sound in the spatial direction towards which the body moved.

i) Felt Water (P4). A wearable that increases sensations of balance and proprioception through feeling and hearing water moving on the body, the water reacting to the person's moves.

Figure 7: Ideas for future sensory technology: a) Soothing Dress; b) Tension-Less; c) Apnea; d) Massaging Pants; e) Power Suit; f) Spatial Center of Gravity; g) The Weight of Tiredness; h) Balance Soundscape; i) Felt Water. Details in the Supplementary Material.

5 DISCUSSION

We discuss various design takeaways and strategies to work with body sensations. We also reflect on the limitations, novelty and contribution of our work.

5.1 Design Takeaways

Working with body sensations as design material was valuable to explore the design space of sensation alterations fostered by sensory stimuli - in multiple ways. First, it encouraged participants to inquire into very **intimate aspects of their daily somatic experiences**, which many found meaningful, valuable and enriching, as expressed by P6: *[it] is important to devote time to exploring my body and sensations*. A heightened sensitivity to their somatic experiences fostered **self-compassion** in some participants, as exemplified by P3's quote: *as I became more conscious about [my body experience], I allowed myself to be more respectful and compassionate towards myself*.

Secondly, through exploring various movement and sensory stimuli potentials, participants realized that they could **shape body sensations through design**. P2 articulated: *[the study] taught me to know how to identify what I want to do with a sensation and find ways to change it. The importance of this is that before [the study], I did not even consider this as an option*. In the final questionnaire, participants shared how these movement and sensory explorations affected them. Several highlighted how the explorations allowed them to **probe their body perception in holistic ways**, e.g.: *I was able to investigate the existing relationship between an emotion, a sensation and the movement I am performing* (P10). A few were surprised with the **sensory objects' capacity to shape their body perception**, as P3 noted: *It was impactful to see that through engaging with everyday-life objects I could experience new sensations, or alter the ones I already felt*. Some reflected that these explorations *opened my sensory capacity and creativity, especially in terms of seeing objects beyond utilitarian terms* (P4).

Finally, regarding sketching concepts for future technology, our approach afforded participants very **intimate and individualized design concepts** that were highly meaningful for each one of them - rather than superficial, shallow or pre-defined experiences. Exploring the interplays between body sensations, movement, and sensory stimuli as design material proved to be highly **generative and conducive to design**, helping shape initial appreciations into concrete design concepts. None of the participants had prior design

experience, but the focus on their own body sensations allowed them to design from an intimate place that valued their lived experience and knowledge. Many found this to be **empowering**, and enabled them to think of themselves as capable of meaningful design. Others mentioned that designing with their own sensations instilled confidence in their creative abilities, inspiring some to be *more creative in [my own work]*, as *I feel confident and inspired* (P5).

For us researchers, body sensations proved to be a valuable sensitizing and generative material that yielded many relevant insights and ideas for future designs. They also helped **create frames to inquiry** deeply into other people's body experiences, to jointly explore them in design.

The movement and sensory potentials (Sections 4.2.1, 4.2.2) constitute concrete design takeaways. While some need further research for confirmation, others align with prior work, e.g. the potential of using different haptic stimuli to bring awareness to the body has also been extensively studied in other soma design projects (through e.g. heat, vibration, or pressure [36, 38, 49, 113, 122, 123]). Our empirics substantiate this and extend it with their potential to also reduce sensations. The sound potential that low pitch amplifies negative sensations is found in prior work (e.g. footsteps' sounds that have been modified to sound at a lower frequency make people feel heavier [95]). Slowing down movements to heighten body awareness has also been used effectively, as seen in installations [22]. The use of cold and heat to intensify or reduce sensations has also been found in prior works [49].

5.1.1 Strategies to Design with Body Sensations. We discuss key methodological strategies that were valuable to us. We also connect them to prior work to provide additional references to the reader to conduct similar methodological approaches.

Accessing, Articulating and Documenting Body Sensations. As body sensations are inherently elusive [42], being conscious of them can be difficult [34, 42, 83]. For us, involving dancers as expert participants meant collaborating with individuals already attuned to self-awareness, body reflection, and expression through movement. Dancers were very capable of both interiorizing our instructions and turning their attention to their sensations. Yet, methodologically, it remained crucial to *facilitate their awareness* for the context of the study. We accomplished this by *incorporating an extensive sensitizing phase*, which participants deemed useful to become aware and deepen their understanding of body sensations, e.g.: *[the exercises] made me question the differences among nuances of these sensations*

(P1) and *[it made me] feel more connected with my body sensations, I know them better now* (P5). It also enabled them to trace connections among sensations and other aspects e.g.: *[the exercises] allowed me to deepen my experience of the relationship that exists between emotion, sensation or movement* (P1). Other designers and researchers can get inspiration from our methods and previous methods in the wider HCI literature on articulating body experiences, e.g. Focusing [65], Feldenkrais [30], slow walking [108], embodied sketching [59] or other soma design methods (see e.g. [30, 32, 107, 113, 122]).

To assist dancers in articulating their body experience we used questionnaires, body maps, informal interviews and somatic enactments during our explorations. They provided nuanced descriptions of their experiences with movement, sensation, and sensory stimuli. By prompting them to articulate their experiences verbally and textually in addition to their somatic expression, we made them conducive to design. It helped dancers clarify and share their experience with others who might not understand certain somatic expressions. In addition to ours, other methods that we have not applied, e.g. micro-phenomenology [72], can also aid in these articulations. Lastly, tools like questionnaires and body maps helped us *document sensations with nuance for future reflection, analysis, and sharing*, which is challenging due to their elusive nature [111]. Our work and related works, such as alternative body maps [2, 110] or response cards [79] (overview in [111]) provide valuable tools.

Sharing and Empathizing with Body Sensations Working with intimate body experiences poses challenges in achieving a shared understanding among people. It is difficult to fully grasp someone else's sensations, and collectively engage with them in design. While recognizing that fully experiencing another person's sensations is impossible, we encouraged participants to verbally and somatically convey their sensations to others. We encouraged others to integrate this information into their own experience, to sensitively relate to the shared body sensation from a 1st person perspective, creating a ground for mutual understanding. To some, it triggered memories of past sensations, e.g. *I became aware of some sensations that, without being mine at that moment, I had experienced at some point in my life* (P3). Our considerations, along with other works (e.g. [24, 57, 59, 63, 112]), provide inspiration for how to share and empathize with others' somatic experiences.

The body sensations participants shared in HE1 (Sec. 4.1.1) were very sensitive and intimate, making it crucial to *create a comfortable space* for them to share their experience. We addressed this through a combination of home exercises and in-person workshops. Home exercises allowed participants to explore their sensations intimately and choose which ones they wanted to share in workshops. In workshops, we facilitated social connections through warm-up activities [60] and created small groups to work in more intimate spaces. We explicitly offered participants the option not to share their sensations, and conducted thorough debriefings after each exercise to reflect on the workshop's impact. These considerations, informed by previous work [24, 71], can assist others in addressing vulnerabilities in design processes.

5.2 Limitations and Future Work

Our study has limitations. Activities were conducted at different times, but body sensations are context-dependent and variable.

Participants may have shared sensations in HE1 that were not experiencing, or experienced differently, in WS1. Future research should address the transient nature of body sensations. Our explorations mostly took place in an academic setting. Future research should delve deeper into individual, contextual, and sociocultural factors.

Further, we incurred some simplifications to give participants actionable structures for their inquiry. While we encouraged them to focus on both positive and negative sensations, some experiences may not have fit these categories and thus went unreported. Additionally, we provided action verbs (i.e. intensify, reduce, bring awareness, transform) to prompt participants to consider potential things to explore in regard to their body sensations. Despite the opportunity to select their own verbs, participants focused on the ones provided. This could stem from dancers being more accustomed to accessing and demonstrating their body sensations (as they generously did throughout the study) than *doing something with them* through design. This is captured by P2's earlier quote (Sec. 5.1), which highlights that before the study he did not consider the possibility of changing his sensations. Offering action verbs may have limited the exploration space, but they provided a generative constraint for participants to engage with the design process.

Working with dancers was valuable in many ways, as they were highly capable of both introspecting and vividly communicating their body experiences. Yet, working with populations less inclined towards introspection and expressive articulation may present challenges - for which our strategies (Sec. 5.1.1) may help.

Our approach focused on surfacing a breadth of experienced sensations and show how they can be worked in design as a way to explore the space body perception alterations through sensory feedback. We see two natural next steps. First, similar to previous soma design processes, we aim to narrow future explorations on particular sensations (e.g. balance in [50, 107]) and their interaction with identified sensory potentials. This can lead to deeper investigations into particular sensations and new design concepts. Second, we plan to implement some of the generated ideas (Sec. 4.3) into prototypes for further exploration and evaluation. For instance, we have begun developing the "Felt Water" ¹ concept into an interactive prototype (see Supplementary Material). We are currently exploring its potential to alter body perception with the dancers.

Finally, our work requires validation through further studies. Firstly, The movement and sensory potentials, although some validate prior works' insights, need to be explored further. Hence, they should be taken here as providing an initial design space that opens for future explorations. Secondly, our work shows that the approach itself yields sensations' alterations. However, the impact of these alterations on interrelated aspects of body perception (see Sec. 4.1.1) can only be evaluated through future comprehensive technology evaluations. The generated design concepts need to be implemented and evaluated to validate the potential of the approach in yielding *interactive technology* that can foster meaningful body perception alterations. Thirdly, future studies applying our

¹Among the nine ideas, we have chosen to implement first "Felt Water" due to two reasons: 1) it obtained a more positive response during the presentation of video prototypes, and most participants expressed a keen interest in trying it out themselves. 2) This idea encompassed elements from other ideas, from HE2 (beyond P4's) which could make it interesting for others' experience, e.g.: sonifying movements with water sounds to emphasize a sensation of flowing movements (P5), using sonification for balance (P6), and a desire to increase proprioception (P7).

approach, methods or strategies are required to further validate aspects of our methodological approach in other contexts. However, it is important to notice that our aim here is not to provide a prescriptive set of methods or fully replicable methodological steps - something that is out of scope in soma design processes that value the subjective and contextual nature of design [30]. Rather, our methodological contributions should be taken as inspiration for others to use, adapt and appropriate in their own design processes.

5.3 Contributions

We contribute methodological design knowledge to explore the design space of body perception alterations fostered by sensory feedback. Our proposed approach centers on body sensations as design material, and in a deep somatic engagement with sensations, sensory stimuli and movement. Our approach draws from and resonates with a growing body of soma design approaches in HCI (e.g. [22, 31, 33, 36, 49, 64, 65, 107, 108, 113]) that center the somatic engagement with the design materials to design meaningful and engaging interactive experiences. We contribute to this body of work in two ways: first, with a collection of methods (Section 3) and strategies (Section 5.1.1) that can provide inspiration to engage with body sensations in design. Secondly, by centering the design inquiry on body perception alterations we help expand a common focus in soma design on deepening body awareness and self-discovery (e.g. [33, 36, 90–92, 107]) towards also fostering perceptual transformations.

Our work can be relevant for multiple HCI communities interested in exploring and designing novel and meaningful body perception alterations facilitated by sensory technologies, or in working with body sensations as design material. For example, multisensory HCI (e.g. [11, 62, 100, 120]), soma design (e.g. [30, 33]), human-computer integration [58, 89], embodied interaction (e.g. [59, 93, 121]), and particular application domains (e.g. sports, games, rehabilitation [49, 56, 57, 85, 117]). Researchers within those communities can find inspiration in our methods (Sec. 3), sensory potentials (Sec. 4.2), strategies (Sec. 5.1.1) and overall approach. Our work can have particular value for those less experienced in working with body sensations as also find theoretical (Sec. 2.1) and empirical (Sec. 4.1.1) grounding on interrelated facets of body perception.

Finally, we also add further empirical evidence to prior HCI work on dancers as a valuable expert population to work in body-centric design processes [51, 78, 114]; and contribute methodologically and empirically to recent calls for works that illustrate how to co-shape the materiality of objects and bodies in design [66].

6 CONCLUSION

Sensory technologies have the capacity to profoundly influence our body perception. As these technologies become more available and ubiquitous, and maybe eventually fulfill their promise to significantly impact health and well-being [47, 61, 62, 85, 96], creativity [21, 114, 115] and even everyday life [115], it will become increasingly important to design interactive experiences that are meaningful, impactful and ethical for individuals [114, 115]. For that, we believe that is not enough with the hypothesis-driven approaches through which most body perception alteration technologies are being designed in communities such as e.g. multisensory HCI (e.g.

[95]). We need approaches that center the felt, somatic experience of people to design interactive experiences that improve their intimate ways of perceiving their own body. Drawing from soma design, in this paper we contribute a methodological approach focused on body sensations as a way to explore and design interesting interplays between sensory stimuli and body perception alterations. Engaging in the design process and approach in itself was impactful and meaningful for the participants. While future empirical work is needed, this insight highlights that engaging in the *methodological process* in itself might be a powerful way for people to alter their relationship with their own body. We hope our work offers design inspiration for others to engage meaningfully with this area.

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